

HISTO-MRI Project

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 Programme under grant agreement no 737180— HISTO-MRI

D1.1: Web site and logo

Version	Date	Reviewer
1.0	30 th June 2017	José M. Benlloch
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1 Deliverable description

This deliverable describes the web site and logo designed for the project.

This deliverable is the first result of *Task 5 Dissemination and Exploitation*, part of **WP1 – Management**.

2 Web Site

A dedicated web site has been created to explain the project aims and objectives, as well as providing general information about HISTO-MRI project activities and the results achieved. This is part of the project communication activities and the strategy of the HISTO-MRI consortium for spreading information about the project. The address of the website is: www.histo-mri-i3m.upv.es

The following chapters describe each of the sections of the web site.

2.1 Home

This section provides a description of the objectives of the project and shows a map with all the participants.

The screenshot shows the top section of the HISTO-MRI Project website. It features a purple logo on the left, followed by the title "HISTO-MRI PROJECT" in bold black text, and the subtitle "In situ imaging of living tissues with cellular spatial resolution" in a smaller font. Below this is a horizontal navigation menu with links for "Home", "Participant Partners", "Public Results", "News", and "Contact Info". The main content area below the menu contains the project title "In situ imaging of living tissues with cellular spatial resolution", the coordinator's name "Coordinator: José M. BENLLOCH", and the project number "Project Number: 737180". A bolded statement reads: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 737180". Below this text is the European Union flag, and at the bottom, a paragraph describes the project's main objective: "The main objective of HISTO-MRI project is to develop the technologies that will enable the non-invasive visualization of individual human cells in vivo and in real time, based on a radical new Magnetic Resonance Imaging concept: High Frequency Pulsed MRI. To accomplish this ambitious objective, several new challenging multidisciplinary

new field of research, pulsed MRI in the high frequency regime, which will radically advance MRI performance to micron resolution.

A Proof of Concept of the new technology will be accomplished through the visualization of a mouse brain at the neuron level. This new technology will enable transformative research in the fields of neurosciences, bioengineering, biophysics and experimental oncology.

It also indicates that the project has received funding from the European Commission under H2020 Programme.

2.2 Participants

This section provides a description of the participants in the project.

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Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

Institute for Instrumentation in Molecular Imaging (I3M)

The Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC) is the largest public multidisciplinary research organisation in Spain. CSIC collaborates with national and International universities, public RTD organisations, SMEs, companies and other institutions of a scientific/technological nature. It has a staff of more than 13,500 employees, among these about 3,500 are permanent researchers and more than 4,000 are pre- and post-doctoral researchers. The CSIC has 135 institutes or centres distributed throughout Spain, including 51 Joint Research Units with universities or other research institutions. There is also a delegation in Brussels. It has considerable experience in both participating and managing RTD projects and training of research personnel. Under the 6th Framework Programme CSIC has signed 404 actions (of which 37 coordinated by CSIC). CSIC has been the 5th organisation in Europe in project execution and funding in the 6th Framework Programme. Under the 7th Framework Programme CSIC has signed more than 440 projects (including 42 coordinated by CSIC as well as 22 ERC).

The Institute participating in the HISTO-MRI Project is the Institute for Instrumentation in Molecular Imaging (I3M – www.i3m.upv.es). I3M is a joint Institute of CSIC- CIEMAT and the Polytechnic University of Valencia (UPV) dedicated to molecular imaging devices development. I3M members have 15 years of experience in sensors and systems for medical imaging. The group has developed several PET and SPECT systems for biomedical studies with small animals, with innovative and patented designs. It has developed a PET mammograph of excellent resolution (below 2mm), within the framework of the EU project MAMMI (Mammography with Molecular Imaging-FP6-2005-LIFESCIHEALTH-7-037555). More recently, it is participating in FP7 coordinating a EU Project to develop a multimaging system PET-MR to accurately diagnose schizophrenia diseases, the MindView project.

Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC)

The LUMC is a modern university medical centre for patient care and clinical research. It has 700 beds and 7000 co-workers. The Department of Radiology has 300 co-workers, and performs both clinical work on patients, as well as a number of imaging projects involving MRI, PET/CT, ultrasound and interventional imaging.

Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft

Fraunhofer Gesellschaft

The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft is the leading organization for applied research in Europe. Its research activities are conducted by 67 institutes and research units at locations throughout Germany. The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft employs a staff of 24,000, who work with an annual research budget totaling more than 2.1 billion euros. The Fraunhofer Institute for Integrated Circuits IIS is one of the world's leading application-oriented research institutions for microelectronic and IT system solutions and services. It ranks first among all Fraunhofer Institutes in size. With the creation of mp3 and the co-development of AAC, Fraunhofer IIS has reached worldwide recognition. In close cooperation with partners and clients the Institute provides research and development services in the following areas: Audio & Multimedia, Imaging Systems, Energy Management, IC Design and Design Automation, Communication Systems, Positioning, Medical Technology, Sensor Systems, Safety and Security Technology, Supply Chain Management and Non-destructive Testing. About 950 employees conduct contract research for industry, the service sector and public authorities. Founded in 1985 in Erlangen, Fraunhofer IIS has now 13 locations in 10 cities: in Erlangen (headquarters), Nuremberg, Fürth, Dresden, further in Bamberg, Waischenfeld, Coburg, Würzburg, Ilmenau and Deggendorf. The budget of 130 million euros is mainly financed by projects. 22 percent of the budget is subsidized by federal and state funds.

The Fraunhofer IIS Department of Magnetic Resonance and X-Ray Imaging developed from the Research Center "Magnetic Resonance Bavaria" (MRB) is an international expert in the research

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- Ultra stable power supplies
- Beam diagnostics
- Insertion devices, undulators and wigglers
- Ion accelerators and ion sources
- Turn-key systems, electron & ion synchrotrons, and microtrons

Installation, commissioning and after-sales service Danfysik accelerator systems Our turn-key accelerator systems and injection booster synchrotrons can be found across the globe. In the near future, our know-how in accelerator systems will help treating cancer patients at ultimate precision with protons, carbon and/or light ions. At the cutting edge of technology our commitment to research and development ensures that we can supply state-of-the-art accelerator technology to the highest industry standard. We recently added Green Magnets, to a range of magnets with close-to-zero energy consumption, to our product line. The ultimate in environmentally friendly magnets saves up to 80% in total ownership costs. At Danfysik we produce the most compact magnet systems on the market for synchrotron light sources, with considerable potential savings. Our superconducting magnets based on second generation High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) represent yet another technological breakthrough.

Ownership and workforce

Danfysik A/S is 100% owned by the Danish Technological Institute and have a staff of more than 100 Physicists, engineers, technicians and administrative. Danfysik A/S has been in business for more than 50 years.

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Tesoro Imaging

The Company is a spin-off from two leading imaging device research centres, the Institute for Molecular Imaging Instrumentation (I3M), a publicly funded Spanish institution, and Weinberg Medical Physics LLC (WMP), a US company based in Bethesda, Maryland. The promoters decided to incorporate the spin-off in Spain in 2012 to exploit, in the medical imaging field, the patents and technologies that WMP had been developing over several years and in which 5 million dollars of federal funds had been invested. The goal of this company is to develop MR scanners, using additive manufacturing techniques, that provide extremely high spatial resolution (≤ 20 microns) using ultra-fast and ultra-strong magnetic fields.

PROJECT COORDINATOR

Prof. Jose M. Benlloch

Institute for Instrumentation in Molecular Imaging,
I3M

2.3 Public results

This section will include all the results that will be available for the general public, including all the deliverables with a Public dissemination level.

HISTO-MRI PROJECT

In situ imaging of living tissues with cellular spatial resolution

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2.4 News

This section will include all news published with information about the project and the press releases issued by the consortium.

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2.5 Contact info

This section provides information to contact the project coordinator.

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In situ imaging of living tissues with cellular spatial resolution

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Project Coordinator

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3 Logo

A dedicated logo has been created. It will be used in all dissemination material to be used.

